

FORMATION OF LOCAL PLASTIC DEFORMATION AREAS IN THE DEFORMATION ZONE DURING DEFORMING BROACHING OF WORKPIECES WITH THROUGH DEFORMATIONS

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Abstract

The article examines some aspects of the technological operation of plastic deformation of holes – deforming broaching. It is used for the manufacture of new and restoration of worn hollow cylindrical products. The article presents experimental data and simulation results aimed at refining the geometric characteristics of the deformation zone during the deforming broaching of cylindrical workpieces with through plastic deformation. It is shown that when the critical pressure is reached in the contact zone between the working surface of the tool and the processed hole of the workpiece, areas of local plastic deformation occur at the beginning and end of contact. This leads to a change in the geometric parameters of the deformation zone, which in turn affects the dimensional and quality parameters of the finished product. The appearance of critical contact pressure corresponds to the critical wall thickness, and its value depends on the tension on the element and the inclination angle of the working element's generatrix. The dependence obtained for its determination. At contact pressures below the critical value, the deformation zone diagram corresponds to the known diagram, which consists of a contact area and two non-contact zones connected to it. At contact pressures greater than the critical value, areas of local plastic deformation appear in the deformation zone diagram at the points where the contact area connects with the non-contact zones.

Keywords: deforming broaching, deforming element, deformation zone, plastic deformation, finite element method, diamond-containing spot method.

Introduction

Deforming broaching (DBR) is a process of cold plastic deformation of cylindrical pipe workpieces made of plastic metals, in which the working deforming elements (DE) are moved with tension along the processed hole. DBR has a number of advantages over cutting hole processing: improvement of the physical and mechanical properties of the processed product material; it reduces the time required for subsequent thermal and chemical-thermal operations by refining the metal structure; it preserves the integrity of the material when restoring worn parts by redistributing the product material to worn areas; there is no negative impact of the process on the environment [1-3]. Therefore, this article discusses some features of deformation in the deformation zone during DBR of products with through deformations.

Literature Review

To obtain the required dimensional parameters and quality indicators of the surface layer of the processed product, the workpiece must go through a deformation stage from its initial state, during which changes in the stress-strain state (SSS) of the material occur. These changes take place in the deformation zone.

The most objective study of the deformation zone during DBR was conducted experimentally at the V.M. Bakul Institute for Superhard materials of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine and presented in [2] in the form of a diagram (Fig. 1), which shows the kinematic and geometric parameters of the deformation zone.

Fig. 1. Deformation zone diagram [2]

The validity of this diagram has been repeatedly proven by other scientists in later works [4-8]. According to it, the deformation zone consists of the contact area between the deforming element and the workpiece – II, and two non-contact zones I and III connected to it (Fig. 1). It should be noted that deformation in different areas of the deformation zone is a single process of product plastic forming and simultaneously determines its stress-strain state and parameters dependent on it in all three areas.

The authors of [2] determined the geometric parameters of the zone using experimental methods and

Fig. 2. Dependence of the non-contact zone height (h/r_0) behind the contact area (curve 1); length of non-contact zones: behind the contact area (l_3/r_0) (curve 2), in front of the contact area (l_2/r_0) (curve 3); the length of the contact zone (l_c/r_0) (curve 4) from the thickness of the workpiece t_0/r_0 [4]; experimental data [2]: \circ – steel 20; Δ – steel 10

The theoretical model presented in [4] provides reasonable results for calculating the geometric parameters of the deformation zone, but only when processing shell-type parts ($t_0/r_0 < 0,1$). The authors link the increase in contact length when machining thick-walled workpieces (Fig. 2, curve 4) to the occurrence of critical contact pressure in the contact zone, which leads to the formation of a front zone of local plastic deformation in the form of a bulge. The authors do not provide the reason for the extreme nature of the non-contact zone height beyond the contact area (Fig. 2, curve 1).

The complexity of theoretical description, labor intensity, and insufficient accuracy of experimental methods require the use of modern numerical analysis methods, in particular the finite element method (FEM), to study the stress-strain state and shape formation of parts during DBR. Research using FEM was carried out in [7] to study the SSS of each section of the deformation zone when modeling the DBR of a workpiece made of low-plastic material – EN-GJL-200 gray cast iron. The authors simulated the deformation of the workpiece only in the surface layer of the hole, but confirmed the results of earlier studies that the processed material on the inner surface of the hole in the deformation zone at the contact area is under conditions of triaxial volumetric compression.

FEM is also used to study SSS during radial swaging of tubular workpieces [9-11]. The deformation process in such an operation is similar to DBR. In [9], the flow of materials in steel tubular workpieces with different wall thicknesses during rotary swaging of pipes with axial feed without mandrel was investigated. The

research was carried out in ABAQUS software based on a 2D axisymmetric finite element model. The authors of the work also found areas of local plastic deformation at the inlet and outlet of the reduction zone. They noted that the deformation of both the outer and inner surfaces of the pipe depends on the wall thickness of the workpiece and the friction coefficient. However, the absence of a specific deformation zone prevented them from establishing the causes of these local areas.

Therefore, to establish the causes of non-monotonic changes in the geometric parameters of the deformation zone, simulation modeling of the DBR process should be performed. Comparison of the simulation results with experimental data will allow verifying the adequacy of the developed models and creating a scientifically sound basis for the development of effective DBR technological processes.

Research Methodology

To conduct experimental studies to determine the length of the contact zone between the deforming element and the workpiece during DBR, a well-known method [2] was used, which consists in applying two diamant-containing spots 4 in diametrically opposite directions to the inner surface 3 of the workpiece 2 (Fig. 3). It is recommended to place spots 4 made of powdered abrasive, which should be harder than the DE material, in the middle of the workpiece length to eliminate the influence of edge effects on the measurement. After performing DBR, characteristic marks in the form of scratches 5 remain on the surface of DE 1, which reflect the contact length.

Fig. 3. Diagram of diamond-containing spots application for contact length determination

Pipes made of 12KhN3A steel were used as workpieces. 12KhN3A steel is widely used for the manufacture of parts such as bushings, sleeves, cylinders, piston pins, and the like, which operate under conditions of increased mechanical and tribological loads and require high wear resistance of surface layers. The choice of 12KhN3A as the base material for studying the DBR process has scientific and practical significance. At the same time, the approaches developed and the results of DBR research can be extended to other products made of structural and alloy steels, as well as non-ferrous alloys with a sufficient level of material plasticity.

Before conducting the research, the workpieces were prepared on a lathe. The length of all workpieces was set to 150 mm, the diameter of the hole was 40 mm, and the diameters of the outer surface were: first group – 44 mm, second – 52 mm, third – 60 mm. This allowed us to conduct research on workpieces with different wall thicknesses: $t_0/d_0 = 0.05; 0.15$ and 0.25 .

Fig. 4. Deforming element

The general methodology for simulating the DBR process in DEFORM 2D/3D™ V 11.0 software is described in articles [6, 12]. The length of the contact zone was determined as follows: in the Deform post-processor, the simulation step was displayed at which

the DE is located in the central part of the workpiece along the axis during processing, and based on the simulation results, the normal pressure diagram on the inner surface of the workpiece was observed (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Determination of the contact length of the workpiece surface with the conical surface DE during DBR simulation

Using the “measurement” tool, the length of the contact zone of the workpiece inner surface with a conical surface DE was recorded according to the normal pressure diagram (Fig. 5).

The height of the non-contact zone during DBR was determined based on the results of simulating the

displacement of a pre-created point on the inner surface of the workpiece. The result of the points displacement from their initial position (before processing) in the radial direction is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Displacement of tracked points in the radial direction

Based on the obtained results, the height of the non-contact zone can be determined as the difference between the maximum displacement of point 1 obtained by computer simulation, which is tied to the hole surface, and the known diameter of the cylindrical land of the DE.

The length l_2 was determined by the difference between the Y coordinate of point P1 when it was at the top of the non-contact zone and the contact end point of the workpiece surface with DE.

Results and Discussion

Fig. 7 shows the summary results of experimental studies and simulation modeling of the DBR process with determination of the contact zone length between the deforming element and the workpiece when changing the wall thickness of the workpiece, the tension on the deforming element (Fig. 7, a) and the angle of the working cone of the deforming element (Fig. 7, b).

Fig. 7. Dependence of contact length on wall thickness in the simulation of deformation by an element: a) with angle $\alpha = 4^\circ$ and tension on the element a/d_0 : 1 – 0.0375; 2 – 0.025; 3 – 0.0125; b) with tension $a/d_0 = 0.025$ and angle α : 1 – 2° ; 2 – 8°
 - - - - experimental results, — simulation results

Fig. 7 confirms that as the thickness of the workpiece increases, the contact length initially decreases and then begins to increase, with a clear inflection point in the function $l_2 = f(t_0/d_0)$ in the region of critical wall thickness. Using statistical processing of the presented results, we can determine the value of the critical

wall thickness at which critical contact pressure occurs in the contact zone:

$$(t_0/d_0)_{cr} = 0,07 + 3,46 a/d_0, \tag{1}$$

The results of simulation modeling regarding the height of the non-contact zone (Fig. 8) confirm its extreme nature depending on the wall thickness of the processed workpiece.

Fig. 8. Change in the height of the non-contact zone obtained by simulation of the DBR process

To identify the reasons for the extreme nature of the contact zone length and the height of the non-contact zone behind the contact area when changing the thickness of the workpiece, let us consider the stress-

strain state of the material in the deformation zone obtained by simulation modeling of the DBR process (Fig. 9).

Fig. 9. Change in stress intensity and strain rate ξ on the hole surface during deformation of 12KhN3A steel workpieces with tension on the element $a/d_0 = 0.025$, angle $\alpha = 4^\circ$: a) $t_0/d_0 = 0.05$; b) $t_0/d_0 = 0.35$

The figure shows that the stress intensity on the hole surface gradually increases as the deforming element passes through, but at the beginning of the non-contact zone “III,” there is a local drop in stress intensity to $\sigma = 450$ MPa in a thin-walled part (Fig. 9, a) and to $\sigma = 270$ MPa in a thick-walled part (Fig. 9, b). In addition, a slight drop in stress intensity in the second case is also observed at the beginning of the contact zone.

Changes in these areas of stress-strain state are also confirmed by changes in the strain rate. The insignificant value of the strain rate of the thin-walled part metal increases to $\xi = 0.03$ 1/sec, while in the thick-walled part it reaches $\xi = 0.08$ 1/sec at the beginning of the contact zone and $\xi = 0.16$ 1/sec. at the end of the contact zone. Therefore, it should be noted that with

an increase in wall thickness, the change in strain rate increases.

The above indicates that when the contact pressure reaches a critical value, which increases with increasing wall thickness at the beginning and end of contact between the deforming element and the processed surface of the workpiece, areas of local plastic deformation occur. The front zone is caused by the material flowing out of the contact area into the front non-contact zone, reducing its length and increasing the contact zone. The rear zone is caused by the material flowing out of the contact area into the non-contact zone behind the deforming element, which leads to a reduction in the height of the non-contact zone.

To confirm this fact, let us consider Fig. 10, which shows the points of contact between the processed material and the cylindrical section of the deforming element depending on the wall thickness.

Fig. 10. Areas of the non-contact zone behind the contact zone that are in contact with the cylindrical area of the deforming element during the deformation simulation of workpieces with tension on the element $a/d_0 = 0.025$, angle $\alpha = 4^\circ$, and wall thickness t_0/d_0 : a) 0.05; b) 0.35

The figure shows that on thin-walled workpieces (Fig. 10, a) there is no contact between the cylindrical land and the machined surface. As the wall thickness increases, the contact pressure increases, causing axial flow of the machined material from the contact area to the non-contact zone. This is evidenced by the appearance of contact between the workpiece material and the cylindrical land (Fig. 10, b). A similar fact of material flow from the contact zone was obtained by the authors [7], who simulated the contact interaction of a cast iron workpiece during its distribution with a conical punch with radial displacement.

As mentioned in the introduction, it is the deformation zone that affects the dimensional parameters and quality indicators of the surface layer of the processed product. Therefore, changing the height of the non-contact zone will affect the final dimensions of the finished product.

Conclusions

1. It has been established that during deforming broaching in conditions where critical contact pressure is present in the deformation zone, areas of local plastic deformation occur at the junctions between the contact area and the non-contact zones.

2. It has been confirmed that the contact length of the deforming element with the machined surface changes non-monotonically with increasing wall thickness – first decreasing and then increasing due to the appearance of a local plastic deformation zone, which reduces the front non-contact zone and increases the contact area.

3. If there is critical contact pressure in the contact zone, material flows from the contact area onto the cylindrical land of the deforming element, which leads to a reduction in the height of the non-contact zone behind the deforming element.

References

1. Posviatenko E. K., et al. Inzheneriia detalei, obroblenykh protiahuianniam [Engineering of parts processed by broaching]. INM im. Bakulia NAN Ukrainy, CNTU MON Ukrainy. Kropyvnytskyi: Ly-senko V. F., 2021, 466 p.
2. Rozenberg A. M., Rozenberg O. A. Mekhanika plasticheskogo deformirovaniia v protsessakh rezaniia i deformiruiushchego protigivaniia [Mechanics of plastic deformation in cutting and deforming broaching]. Ed. by Rodin P. R. Kyiv: Naukova Dumka, 1990, 320 p.
3. Nemyrovskiy Y., Posvyatenko E., Sardak S. Technical-economic aspects of the use of technological process of deforming broaching. In: Ivanov V., et al. Advances in Design, Simulation and Manufacturing II.

DSMIE 2019. Lecture Notes in Mechanical Engineering. Springer, Cham, 2020, pp. 238–247. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-22365-6_24

4. Nemyrovskii Ya. B., Tsekhanov Yu. A. Primenenie variatsionnykh printsipov dlia analiza energeticheskikh i kinematicheskikh parametrov protsessa deformiruiushchego protigivaniia [Application of variational principles to analyze energetic and kinematic parameters of deforming broaching]. Rezanie i instrument v tekhnologicheskikh sistemakh. Kharkiv: NTU “KhPI”, 2001, No. 60, pp. 154–159.

5. Tsekhanov Yu. A., Sheikin S. E. Mekhanika formoobrazovaniia zagotovok pri deformiruiushchem protigivaniia [Mechanics of shaping workpieces in deforming broaching]. Voronezh State Technological Academy. Voronezh, 2001, 200 p.

6. Nemyrovskiy Ya. B., Otamanskyi V. V., Melnyk O. L., Shepelenko I. V., Posviatenko N. I. Improving the technology for restoring worn parts based on cold plastic deformation. International Scientific Journal Problems of Tribology, 2024, Vol. 29, No. 3(113), pp. 31–42. <https://doi.org/10.31891/2079-1372-2024-113-3-31-42>

7. Nemyrovskiy Y., Shepelenko I., Storchak M. Plasticity resource of cast iron at deforming broaching. Metals, 2023, 13(3): 551. <https://doi.org/10.3390/met13030551>

8. Sheykin S. Y., et al. On the contact interaction between hard-alloy deforming broaches and a workpiece during the shaping of grooves in the holes of tubular products. Journal of Superhard Materials, 2021, Vol. 43, pp. 222–230. <https://doi.org/10.3103/S1063457621030096>

9. Liu Y., Liu J., Herrmann M., Schenck C., Kuhfuss B. Material flow in infeed rotary swaging of tubes. Materials, 2021, 14(1): 58, 18 p. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma14010058>

10. Liu Y., Schenck C., Herrmann M., Kuhfuss B. Plastic deformation components in mandrel-free infeed rotary swaging of tubes. Procedia Manufacturing, 2019, Vol. 27, pp. 33–38.

11. Sanjari M., Sapanathan T., Ebrahimi R., Poursina M. Determination of strain field and heterogeneity in radial forging of tube using finite element method and microhardness test. Materials & Design, 2012, Vol. 38, pp. 147–153.

12. Nemyrovskiy Y. B., Shepelenko I. V., Otamanskyi V. V., Melnyk O. L., Vasylyv T. I. Plasticity of workpieces processed by deforming broaching with through deformations. Journal of Engineering Sciences, 2025, Vol. 12(2), pp. D9–D24. [https://doi.org/10.21272/jes.2025.12\(2\).d2](https://doi.org/10.21272/jes.2025.12(2).d2)